

**AWARENESS, UTILIZATION, AND PUPILS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE ON
NON-PRINT BREAKTHROUGH ACHIEVEMENT IN NATION-BUILDING
THROUGH APPLICATION AND SUSTAINABILITY**

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Awareness, Utilization, and Pupils' Academic Performance on Non-Print Breakthrough Achievement in Nation-Building through Application and Sustainability

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Abstract

Non-print resources are vital in academic libraries and classroom instruction (Mubofu, 2022). To enhance 21st-century teaching and learning, Project BANAS (Breakthrough Achievement in Nation-Building through Application and Sustainability), a Social Studies learning innovation, was institutionalized. This study assessed teachers' level of awareness and extent of utilization of BANAS Non-Print Resources in Social Studies classes and their correlation with pupils' academic performance in the Schools Division of Bacolod City. A descriptive-correlational research design was used to test hypotheses, generalize findings, and examine associations between variables. Results revealed that teachers exhibit a very high level of awareness of BANAS non-print resources, with male teachers showing slightly higher awareness than females. Teachers with Doctorate Degrees had the highest awareness, while Master Teacher II scored the highest among positions. The extent of utilization was similarly high, with male teachers utilizing the resources more. Those with Doctorate Degrees reported the highest utilization, while Teacher III maximized usage among positions. No significant differences were found in teachers' awareness or utilization when grouped by sex, educational attainment, or position. However, a significant positive relationship was established between awareness and utilization. Conversely, no significant relationship was found between teachers' awareness or utilization and pupils' academic performance. These findings highlight the potential of Project BANAS in advancing 21st-century education. Further support and targeted training could enhance teachers' effective use of BANAS resources, ultimately contributing to improved student outcomes.

Keywords: *academic performance, non-print, application, sustainability*

Introduction

Non-print resources are vital in academic libraries and classroom instruction (Mubofu, 2022). Mayer et al (2020) likewise found that the inclusion of non-print resources and instructional multimedia is a key strategy for effective learning process. In the Philippines, non-print resources have been incorporated to the learning modalities implemented by basic and higher education schools such as Printed Modular, Digital Modular, and Television-based Instruction (Estrellado, 2021; Galang, 2021). Hence, Mayer (2021), Estrellado (2021), and Galang (2021) conducted local studies that served as foundations in the pursuit of this inquiry.

To significantly improve teaching-learning adept to the 21st century learning styles of learners, the Department of Education has been promoting the use of modern non-print resources such as those accessible in the Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS Guidelines, 2019) and other digital platforms. Locally, the Schools Division of Bacolod City institutionalized the use of competency-based localized print and non-print resources through Division Memorandum No. 157 s. 2024, under Project BANAS (Breakthrough Achievement in Nation-Building through Application and Sustainability). Pioneered in 2018, Project BANAS aims to foster appreciation for cultural heritage while improving teaching-learning outcomes across disciplines.

Despite these efforts, there remains a significant research gap regarding the localized implementation of these resources, particularly in Social Studies instruction. At the national level, while studies such as those by Mayer (2021), Estrellado (2021), and Galang (2021) highlight the integration of non-print resources, they focus on broader implementation and lack emphasis on localized innovations. Locally, Concha's (2023) investigation into Project BANAS materials' impact on learners' academic performance leaves a gap in understanding teachers' awareness and utilization of these resources in Social Studies classes.

The researcher, a Grade 5 Teacher of Asuncion Lopez Lizares Elementary School, Barangay Granada, Bacolod City investigated the level of awareness, extent of utilization of non-print BANAS resources among public elementary school teachers handling Social Studies classes in Bacolod City, and its correlation to pupils' academic performance. Results of this scientific inquiry were anchored on the Division Enhancement Plan based on the prior research conducted; Impact of Project BANAS Materials to the Academic Performance of Learners (Concha, 2023). Findings will inform policy recommendations for SDO Bacolod City to enhance the implementation of Project BANAS Programs, Projects, and Activities (PPAs).

Research Questions

The primary objective of this study is to assess the level of awareness and extent of utilization of BANAS Non-Print Resources of teachers handling Social Studies classes and its correlation to pupil's academic performance in the Schools Division of Bacolod City. In particular, this study aimed to address the following inquiries:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents when grouped according to sex, highest educational attainment, and position?;

2. What is the level of awareness of BANAS Non-Print Resources among public elementary school teachers when taken as a whole and grouped according to profile?;
3. What is the extent of utilization of BANAS Non-Print Resources among public elementary school teachers when taken as a whole and grouped according to profile?;
4. What is the level of pupils' performance on BANAS Non-print resources among public school teachers when taken as a whole and grouped according to profile?;
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of awareness of BANAS Non-Print Resources among public elementary school teachers when grouped according to profile?
6. Is there a significant difference in the extent of utilization of BANAS Non-Print Resources among public elementary school teachers when grouped according to profile?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the level of awareness and extent of utilization of BANAS Non-Print Resources?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' level of awareness and pupils' academic performance on BANAS Non-Print Resources?
9. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' extent of utilization and pupils' academic performance on BANAS Non-Print Resources?
10. What program may be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This correlational research design aims to assess the teachers' level of awareness, extent of utilization, and pupils' performance on BANAS Non-Print Resources. Similarly, the study aims to investigate whether BANAS's level of awareness and extent of utilization differs based on teacher demographics. Furthermore, the study aims to investigate whether a significant relationship exists in the teachers' level of awareness, extent of utilization of BANAS, and pupils' performance.

Quantitative research according to Mohajan (2020) is the investigation of real-world conditions measured through numbers. Additionally, descriptive-correlational research aims to test hypotheses given the numerical data to generalize about a population (Siedlecki, 2020). Specifically, Harrison et al. (2020) describe correlational designs as a means for investigating associations between variables.

Respondents

The subject and respondents of the study were the regular-permanent public elementary teachers who are teaching Araling Panlipunan in the Schools Division of Bacolod City for the School Year 2024-2025.

In the Schools Division of Bacolod City, there is a total of 203 Araling Panlipunan teachers. Using Yamane's Formula, the sample size is 135.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex		
Male	7	5.2
Female	128	94.8
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	102	75.6
Master's Degree	31	23.0
Doctorate Degree	2	1.5
Designation		
Teacher 1-3	125	92.6
Master Teacher	10	7.4

The researcher used simple random sampling in identifying the number of respondents based on the population. Initially, the researcher gathered the population of Araling Panlipunan elementary teachers. Then, the researcher printed the names of the teachers and hand-picked the teachers using the fishbowl sampling to ensure that all teachers have equal chances to be selected. After the random selection, the researcher contacted the teachers to answer the survey questionnaire.

Instrument

The researcher-made survey instrument assessed the level of awareness and extent of utilization of BANAS Non-Print Resources among public elementary school teachers. The instrument had three parts. The first part of the questionnaire contained the rationale, ethical considerations, and demographic profile of the respondents. The second part of the questionnaire contained the level of awareness of BANAS. This part of the questionnaire evaluates the teacher's awareness on the purpose, features, content, and strategies in using non-print BANAS. The third part of the questionnaire contained the extent of utilization of BANAS. This part of the questionnaire evaluates the teacher's extent of utilization of non-print BANAS in terms of instructional planning, implementation, and

evaluation.

Procedure

To gather the data, the researcher submitted a letter seeking the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent for data gathering (see Appendix C.1). Once the permission was secured, transmittal letters were sent to the Education Program Supervisor in Araling Panlipunan, Public Schools District Supervisors, and School Heads seeking their approval to survey the teachers. Then, the participants were oriented on the nature, purpose, and ethical standards of the study. The participants could choose to answer in printed or digital forms of the questionnaire, whichever they preferred.

After the conduct of the survey, the participants were ensured of confidentiality, and the findings of the study were reported to them. Lastly, the researcher gave tokens to the participants as gratitude for the time and expertise they spent in accomplishing the survey.

Data Analysis

After data collection, the researcher tallied, tabulated, and analyzed the gathered data. Robust statistical instruments were used to arrive at sound analysis, implications, and conclusions. Specific to the objectives of the study, the succeeding statements succinctly explain the statistical treatments.

To answer statement of the problem 1, to measure the demographic profile of the respondents when grouped according to sex, highest educational attainment, and position, frequency count and percentage were used.

To answer problem number 2, to measure the level of awareness of BANAS non-print resources among public elementary schools when grouped according to sex, highest educational attainment, and position, mean was used.

For statement 3, the researcher used mean to measure the extent of utilization of BANAS non-print resources among public elementary schools when grouped according to sex, highest educational attainment, and position.

For statement 4, the researcher used mean to measure the pupil’s performance on BANAS non-print resources among public elementary schools when grouped according to sex, highest educational attainment, and position.

For statement 5, to determine the difference in the level of awareness of BANAS non-print resources when grouped according to sex, highest educational attainment, and position, the Mann-Whitney (U) Test and Kruskal Wallis H-Test were used.

For statement 6, to determine the difference in the extent of utilization of BANAS non-print resources when grouped according to sex, highest educational attainment and position, the Mann-Whitney (U) Test and Kruskal Wallis H-Test were used.

For statements 7, to determine the relationships between level of awareness and extent of utilization, Gamma Coefficient were used.

For statement 8, to determine the relationships between the level of awareness and the pupil’s performance, Gamma Coefficient were used.

For statement 9, to determine the relationships between the extent of Utilization and pupils' performance, Gamma Coefficient were used.

Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation and analysis of data gathered in connection with the specific problems and hypotheses of this research work.

It adhered to appropriate procedures consistent with the types of data collected and the methodologies chosen to find answers to each of the problems. The quantitative data gathered from the respondents’ responses to the instrument were tallied, tabulated, and subjected to statistical analysis and interpreted following the objectives.

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the 135 public elementary school teachers in the Division of Bacolod City in terms of sex, highest educational attainment, and position.

Table 2. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Respondents According Profile

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>frequency(f)</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
Sex	Male	7	5.20
	Female	128	94.80
	Total	135	100
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor’s Degree	102	76.30
	Master’s Degree	31	22.20

	Doctorate Degree	2	1.50
	Total	135	100
Position	Teacher 1	61	45.20
	Teacher 2	14	10.40
	Teacher 3	50	37.00
	Master Teacher 1	6	4.40
	Master teacher 2	4	3.00
	Total	135	100

Predominantly of the 135 respondents were female accounting for 94.8 percent (128 individuals) with males accounting for 5.2 percent (7 individuals). Meanwhile in terms of highest educational attainment, 76.3 percent (102 individuals) have Bachelor’s Degree, 22.2 percent (31 individuals) have Master’s Degree, and 1.5 percent (2 individuals) have Doctorate Degree. Lastly, in terms of position, 61 respondents were Teacher 1 accounting for 45.2 percent, 14 were Teacher 2 with 10.4 percent, 50 were Teacher 3 with 37 percent, 6 Master Teacher 1 with 4.4 percent, and 4 Master Teacher 2 with 3 percent.

Level of Awareness on BANAS Non-Print Resources when Taken as a Whole and when grouped according to Profile

Table 3 shows the level of awareness on BANAS non-print resources when taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile.

Table 3. Level of Awareness on BANAS Non-Print Resources According to Profile

Profile	Category	n	mean	Interpretation
Sex	Male	7	3.81	Very High
	Female	128	3.58	Very High
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor’s Degree	103	3.58	Very High
	Master's Degree	30	3.60	Very High
	Doctorate Degree	2	4.00	Very High
Position	Teacher 1	61	3.51	Very High
	Teacher 2	14	3.54	Very High
	Teacher 3	50	3.70	Very High
	Master Teacher 1	6	3.50	Very High
	Master teacher 2	4	3.80	Very High
	As a Whole	135	3.59	Very High

The data analysis indicates that teachers have a very high level of awareness of BANAS non-print resources with the mean of 3.59. In terms of sex, male teachers have a very high level of awareness with a mean of 3.81 followed by female teachers having 3.58 mean. In terms of highest educational attainment, teachers with a Doctorate Degree have the highest level of awareness of BANAS non-print resources with a mean of 4.00 followed by teachers with a Master’s Degree having 3.60 mean, and teachers with a Bachelor’s Degree having 3.58. In terms of position, Master Teacher 2 has the highest level of awareness, with a mean score of 3.80. This is followed by Master Teacher 1, with a mean score of 3.50. Next is Teacher 3, with a mean score of 3.70, followed by Teacher 2, with a mean score of 3.54. Lastly, Teacher 1 with a mean score of 3.51. All groups obtained a very high level of awareness.

The very high level of awareness of BANAS non-print resources among teachers depicts the strong information dissemination of the Division of Bacolod City on its Division Memorandum 157 series of 2024 that provides for the project entitled BANAS (Breakthrough Achievement in Nation-Building through Application and Sustainability). Similarly, the results imply that teachers are informed of BANAS in terms of content, features, purpose, and development process of the said resources.

Hernbloom (2021) noted that content knowledge and teaching approaches are relevant in enhancing learners' academic performance. For this reason, teachers are expected to be aware of BANAS resources so that they can further their content knowledge and manifest such mastery in their instructions Estrellado (2021). Moreover, the Araling Panlipunan learning area must also sustain this very high level of awareness among teachers so that the program will continue to benefit pupils.

Extent of Utilization on BANAS Non-print Resources When taken as a Whole and when grouped according to Profiles

Table 4 presents the extent of utilization on BANAS non-print resources when respondents are taken as a whole and according to profile.

Table 4. Extent of Utilization on BANAS Non-Print Resources According to Profile

Profile	Category	n	mean	Interpretation
Sex	Male	7	3.49	Very High
	Female	128	3.22	high
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelors’ Degree	103	3.27	very high

position	Master's Degree	30	3.10	high
	Doctorate Degree	2	3.6	Very High
	Teacher 1	61	3.24	high
	Teacher 2	14	3.11	high
	Teacher 3	50	3.3	Very High
	Master Teacher 1	6	3.07	high
	Master teacher 2	4	3.15	high
	As a Whole	135	3.24	high

The table shows that teachers have a high extent of utilization of BANAS non-print resources, with a mean score of 3.24. In terms of sex, male teachers demonstrate a very high extent of utilization, with a mean score of 3.49, while female teachers have a high extent of utilization, with a mean score of 3.22. Regarding highest educational attainment, teachers with a Doctorate Degree have the highest extent of utilization, with a mean score of 3.60, followed by teachers with a Bachelor’s Degree, who have a mean score of 3.27, both interpreted as very high. Teachers with a Master’s Degree have a mean score of 3.10, which is interpreted as high extent of utilization. In terms of position, Teacher 3 has the highest extent of utilization, with a mean score of 3.30, interpreted as very high. This is followed by Teacher 1, with a mean score of 3.24. Next are Master Teachers 2, with a mean score of 3.15, and Teacher 2, who follows closely with a mean score of 3.11. Lastly, Master Teachers 1 have a mean score of 3.07, all of which indicate a high extent of utilization.

The results imply that teachers utilize to a high extent BANAS non-print resources in terms of instructional planning, implementation, and evaluation. The results also mean that teachers find BANAS non-print resources relevant to teaching Most Essential Learning Competencies, classroom observation, and additional learning activities to pupils. Importantly, teachers perceive that BANAS non-print section in the library is effective in supplementing their instruction.

Spring (2023) highlights the importance of using high-quality materials in the teaching-learning process. BANAS non-print resources are great examples since the Araling Panlipunan learning area quality-assures these materials. Similarly, teachers utilize these high-quality materials mean quality instructions provided to pupils. Contextualized, localized, and indigenized BANAS non-print resources help teachers deliver and pupils interactively comprehend the lessons (Li, 2022). Therefore, teachers are encouraged to utilize BANAS non-print resources to cater the 21st-century skills among modern pupils.

Level of Pupil's Performance on BANAS Non-print Resources when taken as a whole and when grouped according to Profile.

Table 5 on the next page presents the level of pupil performance on BANAS non-print resources when respondents are taken as a whole and according to profile.

Table 5. *Level of Pupils' Performance on BANAS Non-Print Resources According to Profile*

Profile	Category	n	mean	Interpretation
Sex	Male	7	87.59	Very Satisfactory
	Female	128	86.98	Very Satisfactory
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelors’ Degree	103	87.01	Very Satisfactory
	Master's Degree	30	87.12	Very Satisfactory
	Doctorate Degree	2	85.40	Very Satisfactory
Position	Teacher 1	61	87.00	Very Satisfactory
	Teacher 2	14	86.67	Very Satisfactory
	Teacher 3	50	87.15	Very Satisfactory
	Master Teacher 1	6	86.45	Very Satisfactory
	Master teacher 2	4	87.30	Very Satisfactory
	As a Whole	135	87.01	Very Satisfactory

The results indicate a very satisfactory level of pupils’ performance in Araling Panlipunan, with an average score of 87.01 in the Division of Bacolod City. Male teachers have a mean score of 87.59, while female teachers have a mean score of 86.98, both showing a very satisfactory level of performance.

In terms of highest educational attainment, teachers with a Master’s Degree achieve the highest performance, with a mean score of 87.21. This is followed by teachers with a Bachelor’s Degree, who have a mean score of 87.01, and teachers with a Doctorate Degree, who have a mean score of 85.40. All groups attained a very satisfactory level of pupil performance.

Regarding position, Master Teachers 2 have the highest level of pupil performance, with a mean score of 86.97. Followed by Teacher 3, with a mean score of 87.15. Next are Teacher 1, with a mean score of 87.00, and Teacher 2, with a mean score of 86.67. Finally, Master Teachers 1 have a mean score of 86.45. All of these groups have achieved a very satisfactory level of pupil performance in Araling Panlipunan.

The data imply that Araling Panlipunan teachers effectively deliver their lessons. Moreover, teachers manifest expertise in making

students comprehend the Most Essential Learning Competencies. This further show that Araling Panlipunan learning area is competitive and within the standards of the Department of Education. To some extent, Araling Panlipunan teachers are aware and utilize BANAS resources in their instruction to further the learning of pupils.

Having learning resources, according to Guinto et al. (2021) contribute to pupil performance. BANAS non-print resources provide for this need whereby pupils need learning materials to aid in comprehending their lessons in Araling Panlipunan (Pamintuan, 2021). As such, BANAS non-print resources provide interactive lessons to pupils. Therefore, BANAS non-print resources play significant role in the teaching-learning process.

Difference in the Awareness on BANAS non-print resources according to Sex

Table 6.1 shows the difference in the awareness of BANAS non-print resources according to sex.

Table 6.1. *Difference in the Awareness on BANAS Resources According to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Male	7	87.14
Female	128	66.95
Total	135	

Computed (U) Value: 314.00
P-value: 0.164
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not Significant

Mann Whitney Test was used in Table 6.1 to determine the difference in the awareness of BANAS Non-print resources when teachers are grouped according to their sex. Results showed that the computed value is 314 and the p-value is 0.473. Comparing the p-value and the level of significance, the p-value is greater than 0.5. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the awareness of the teachers according to their sex. Thus, there is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

This suggests that sex does not significantly influence teachers' awareness of BANAS Non-print resources. However, this finding contrasts with Danko et al.'s study, which found that while female instructors use ICT more frequently, male counterparts report higher self-assessed ICT skills and greater confidence in using technology for instruction. This inconsistency indicates that although awareness of specific resources like BANAS may currently be gender-neutral, it could shift over time as trends in technology use and self-perceived proficiency evolve differently for male and female educators.

Difference in the Awareness on BANAS non-print resources according to Highest Educational Attainment

Table 6.2 shows the difference in the awareness on BANAS non-print resources according to highest educational attainment.

Table 6.2. *Difference in the Awareness on BANAS Resources According to Highest Educational Attainment*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Bachelor's Degree	103	67.72
Master's Degree	30	66.43
Doctorate Degree	2	106
Total	135	

Computed (H) Value: 2.12
P-value: 0.346
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not Significant

Kruskal Wallis Test was used in Table 6b to determine the difference in the awareness on BANAS non-print resources when teachers are grouped according to their highest educational attainment. Results showed that the computed value is 2.12 and the p-value is 0.346. Comparing the p-value and the level of significance, the p-value is greater than 0.5. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the awareness on BANAS non-print resources when teachers are grouped according to their highest educational attainment. Thus, there is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

The consistently very high-level awareness of non-print BANAS among teachers regardless of their educational attainment mean that teachers are committed to know this innovation of the Araling Panlipunan learning area. Additionally, teachers also have access to BANAS non-print resources which in turn makes them aware. Teachers also are included in crafting such resources making them highly aware of BANAS non-print resources. Concha et al (2024) note that teachers must be aware of BANAS resources because of its content alignment and impact on pupil performance.

Difference in the Awareness on BANAS non-print resources according to Position

Table 6.3 on the next page shows the difference in the awareness on BANAS non-print resources according to position.

Mann Whitney Test was used in table 6c to determine the difference in the awareness on BANAS Non-print resources according to their position. Results showed that the computed value is 1.506 and the p-value is 0.826. Comparing the p-value and the level of

significance, the p-value is greater than 0.5. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the awareness on BANAS Non-print resources when teachers are grouped according to their position. Thus, there is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

The consistently high extent of utilization of BANAS non-print resources regardless of their position implies that teachers find the usefulness of such resources in their instructions. BANAS non-print resources are sequenced, and comprehensible, thus, teachers utilize such materials. Mayer et al (2021) provide that non-print resources must be utilized in daily instructions to ensure content delivery and modern teaching strategy.

Table 6.3. *Difference in the Awareness on BANAS Resources According to Position*

<i>Position</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Teacher 1	61	65.16
Teacher 2	14	62.79
Teacher 3	50	71.33
Master teacher 1	6	72.42
Master Teacher 2	4	78.38
Total	135	

Computed (H) Value: 1.51
P-value: 0.826
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not Significant

Difference in the Utilization of BANAS Non-print Resources When Grouped According to Sex

Table 7.1 on the next page shows the difference in the utilization of BANAS non-print resources according to sex.

Mann Whitney test was used in table 7.1 to determine the difference in the utilization of BANAS Non-print resources when teachers are grouped according to their sex. Results showed that the computed value is 0.321 and the p-value is 0.202. Comparing the p-value and the level of significance, the p-value is greater than 0.5. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the utilization of BANAS Non-print resources when teachers are grouped according to their sex. Thus, there is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table 7.1. *Difference in the Utilization of BANAS Resources According to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Male	7	86.14
Female	128	67.01
Total	135	

Computed (U) Value: 321.00
P-value: 0.202
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not Significant

The consistent and high-level of extent of utilization encourage teachers regardless of sex continuously seek out new and innovative BANAS materials, fostering a culture of ongoing professional development and improvement in teaching practices. This shows that these resources are not only effective in enhancing student learning but also offer high usability and adaptability, where teachers making them valuable tools in teaching Araling Panlipunan. Beck & Pidgeon, (2020) Using localized non-print resources makes lessons more engaging and relevant.

Difference on the Extent of Utilization of BANAS Non-print Resources according to Educational Attainment

Table 7.2 shows the difference in the utilization of BANAS non-print resources in terms of educational attainment.

Table 7.2. *Difference in the Utilization of BANAS Resources according to Highest Educational Attainment*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Bachelor's Degree	103	70.16
Master's Degree	30	58.53
Doctorate Degree	2	99.00
Total	135	

Computed (H) Value: 3.41
P-value: 0.182
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not Significant

Kruskal Wallis Test was used in table 7.2 to determine the difference in the utilization of BANAS non-print resources when teachers are grouped according to their highest educational attainment. Results showed that the computed value is 3.409 and the p-value is 0.182. Comparing the p-value and the level of significance, the p-value is greater than 0.5.

Therefore, there is no significant difference in the utilization of BANAS non-print resources when teachers are grouped according to their highest educational attainment. Thus, there is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

The consistently high extent of utilization of BANAS non-print resources means that teachers regardless of their highest educational attainment believe in the efficacy of BANAS non-print resources. This shows that BANAS non-print resources are highly usable and practical in teaching lessons in Araling Panlipunan. Teachers believe that teaching resources must be enriched by technology (Pamintuan, 2021). BANAS non-print resources provide for this need, and teachers must supplement their instructions with such resources.

Difference in the Utilization of BANAS Non-print Resources According to Position

Table 7.3 shows the difference in the Utilization of BANAS non-print resources in terms of position.

Table 7.3. *Difference in the Utilization of BANAS Resources according to Position*

<i>Position</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Teacher 1	61	69.16
Teacher 2	14	61.50
Teacher 3	50	70.19
Master teacher 1	6	60.50
Master Teacher 2	4	56.88
Total	135	

Computed (H) Value: 1.17
P-value: 0.883
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not Significant

Mann Whitney Test was used in Table 7.3 to determine the difference in the utilization of BANAS Non-print resources when teachers are grouped according to position. Results showed that the computed value is 1.170 and the p-value is 0.883. Comparing the p-value and the level of significance, the p-value is greater than 0.5. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the utilization of BANAS Non-print resources when teachers are grouped according to position. Thus, there is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

The consistently very high extent of utilization of BANAS non-print resources regardless of teachers' position implies that teachers find the usefulness of such resources in their instructions. Since BANAS non-print resources are sequenced, organized, and comprehensible, teachers utilize such materials in their lessons. Mayer et al (2021) provide that non-print resources must be utilized in daily instructions to ensure content delivery and modern teaching strategy.

Relationship Between the Level of Awareness and Extent of Utilization on BANAS Non-print Resources

Table 8 shows the relationship between the level of awareness and extent of utilization on BANAS non-print resources.

Table 8. *Relationship Between the Level of Awareness and Extent of Utilization on BANAS Resources*

<i>Level of Awareness</i>	<i>Extent of Utilization</i>				<i>Total</i>
	<i>Very High</i>	<i>High</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>Very Low</i>	
Very High	55	40	4	0	99
High	3	23	4	0	30
Low	0	0	4	0	4
Very low	0	0	2	0	2
Total	58	63	14	0	135

Computed (G) value: 0.8277
P-Value: 0.000
Decision: Reject Ho
Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of Significance

Gamma coefficient was used in table 8 to determine the relationship between the level of awareness and the extent of utilization of the respondents on BANAS non-print resources. Results show that the computed value is 0.8277 and the p-value is 0.000. Comparing the p-value and the level of significance, the p-value is greater than 0.5. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the level of awareness and the extent of utilization of the respondents on BANAS non-print resources. Thus, there is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

The correlation between the level of awareness and extent of utilization of BANAS non-print resources among teachers implies that the more aware the teacher is about BANAS non-print resources, the more likely the teacher is to utilize the resources in instructions. Having the knowledge on non-print resources is significant in utilizing such basic tools and techniques to deliver information (Ramlatchan 2019) and lesson content. Multimedia learning theory by Mayer (2021) provides that teachers sequentially are aware and utilize non-print resources in their instructions which ensures effective learning and motivation among pupils (Putri et al., 2022). Kruskal Wallis test was used in table 10 to determine the difference in the level of pupil's performance on BANAS non-print resources when teachers are grouped according to their highest educational attainment. There is no significant difference in level of pupil's performance when teachers are grouped according to their highest educational attainment [$G=.8277, p=0.000$]. Thus, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

The consistently high level of pupil performance in Araling Panlipunan regardless of the teacher's highest educational attainment implies that teachers are successful in delivering the Most Essential Learning Competencies. Araling Panlipunan teachers due to their content knowledge, resourcefulness, and pedagogical expertise provide quality instructions to pupils. Mubofu (2022) notes the practicality of using non-print resources in lesson delivery and Araling Panlipunan teachers utilize BANAS non-print resources for such purpose.

Relationship Between the Level of Awareness and Academic Performance on BANAS Non-print Resources

Table 9 shows the relationship between the level of awareness and academic performance on BANAS non-print resources.

Table 9. Relationship Between the Level of Awareness and Academic Performance on BANAS Print Resource

Level of Awareness	Pupils Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did Not Meet Expectation	
Very High	0	94	5	0	0	99
High	0	29	1	0	0	30
Low	0	4	0	0	0	4
Very low	0	2	0	0	0	2
Total	0	129	6	0	0	135

Computed (G) value: -0.316

P-Value: 0.473

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of Significance

Gamma Coefficient was used in table 9 to determine the relationship between the teachers' level of awareness and the level of pupil's performance on BANAS non-print resources. Results show that the computed value is -0.316 and the p-value is 0.473. Comparing the p-value and the level of significance, the p-value is greater than .05. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the teachers' level of awareness and the level of pupil's performance on BANAS non-print resources. Thus, there is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

The results show that regardless of the awareness of BANAS non-print resources, teachers are effective in the delivery of their lessons and improving pupil performance. Teachers manifest the necessary competence in fulfilling their teaching roles. However, BANAS non-print resources significantly have an impact on the mastery of content among teachers. The awareness of teachers on non-print resources aid in their pedagogy and pupil's performance Noetel et al. (2021).

Relationship Between Extent of Utilization and Academic Performance on BANAS Non-print Resources

Table 10 shows the relationship between extent of utilization and academic performance on BANAS non-print resources.

Table 10. Relationship Between Extent of Utilization and Academic Performance on BANAS Print Resources

Extent of Utilization	Pupil's Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did Not Meet Expectation	
Very High	0	55	3	0	0	58
High	0	60	3	0	0	63
Low	0	14	0	0	0	14
Very low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	129	6	0	0	135

Computed (G) value: -0.231

P-Value: 0.511

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of Significance

Gamma Coefficient was used in table 10 to determine the relationship between the extent of utilization and the pupil's academic performance on BANAS non-print resources. Results show that the computed value is -0.231 and the p-value is 0.511. Comparing the p-value and the level of significance, the p-value is greater than .05. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the extent of utilization and the pupil's academic performance on BANAS non-print resources. Thus, there is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

The results show that regardless of the extent of utilization of BANAS non-print resources, teachers effectively teach and improve pupil performance. Teachers have competence in preparing, implementing, and evaluating instructions which influence pupil performance. Nevertheless, BANAS non-print resources aid teachers in effectively delivering their lessons. Teachers also utilize BANAS non-print resources to improve their daily instructions (Bel & Lowenthal, 2021).

The consistently high level of pupil performance depicts the effectiveness of teachers in lesson delivery regardless of sex and position. Both male and female, teachers 1-3, and master teachers provide quality instructions to their pupils. Relatedly, Araling Panlipunan teachers are aware of and utilize BANAS non-print resources in their instructions which seemingly aid in the successful lesson delivery. Castro-Alonzo et al (2021) provide that non-print resources aid in the successful learning experience of pupils.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Most respondents are female, have Bachelor's Degrees and hold the position of Teacher 1. This means that the teaching staff is mostly female, primarily holds Bachelor's Degrees, and is in the early stages of their careers, with room for growth in education and professional advancement.

When taken as a whole and grouped according to profile, teachers are well-informed about the BANAS Innovation established by Division Memorandum 157 series of 2024 and exhibit very high awareness of its features, development, content, purpose, usage strategies, and library section

The teachers utilize BANAS non-print resources to a high extent for planning, implementing, and evaluating instruction, as well as in delivering Most Essential Learning Competencies during classroom observations and library use.

When taken as a whole and grouped according to profile, all groups regardless of sex, educational attainment, or position demonstrate a very satisfactory level of pupil performance in Araling Panlipunan. This means that Araling Panlipunan teachers are effective in delivering the Most Essential Learning Competencies and aid teachers in their instructions.

Irrespective of their sex, educational attainment, position, public elementary school teachers demonstrate comparable level of awareness on BANAS non-print resources.

Irrespective of their sex, educational attainment, position, public elementary school teachers demonstrate comparable extent of utilization of BANAS non-print resources.

The level of awareness has a significant impact on the extent of utilization of BANAS non-print resources and the more aware the teacher is about BANAS non-print resources, the more likely the teacher is to utilize the resources in instructions.

Regardless of the awareness of BANAS non-print resources, teachers are effective in the delivery of their lessons and improving pupil performance. Teachers manifest the necessary competence in fulfilling their teaching roles.

Regardless of the extent of utilization of BANAS non-print resources, teachers effectively teach and improve pupil performance. Teachers have competence in preparing, implementing, and evaluating instructions which influence pupil performance.

Taking into account the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are put forth:

Since the study found that most respondents are female, it's recommended to actively involve also the male teachers in using the BANAS non-print resources. Additionally, schools may be monitored to ensure that effective implementation of these resources, regardless of teachers' educational attainment or position.

Since teachers already have a very high level of awareness on BANAS non-print resources, schools may provide teachers training and support. Regular workshops will help them stay up-to-date and use these resources effectively. Setting up a feedback system will allow teachers share their experiences and suggest improvements. Encouraging teachers to collaborate and share best practices will also help. Lastly, monitoring the use of these resources and offering extra support as needed will ensure they are being used effectively in all schools.

To support the effective utilization of BANAS non-print resources, it is important to promote strategies for their effective use in library settings and provide training to help integrate these resources into library programs. Additionally, establish a feedback system to collect teachers' experiences and challenges with the resources, and use this feedback to make improvements and offer further support as needed.

To further enhance the very satisfactory pupil performance in Araling Panlipunan, school heads may provide support on the use of BANAS resources by allocating funds to ensure teachers have easy access to these materials. Additionally, conducting School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions would allow teachers to share best practices and strategies for integrating BANAS resources into their instruction. Parents may also be encouraged to access BANAS resources, either through their children's schools or online, to help address their children's learning needs at home.

Although the results show no significant difference in the awareness of BANAS resources based on teacher profiles, it is recommended to continue providing additional support and practical guides to help teachers use these resources more effectively. Additionally, school subject coordinators may regularly monitor the utilization of BANAS resources to ensure they are achieving their intended goals.

Since teachers are already utilizing BANAS non-print resources effectively, it's important to keep supporting their use. Continue offering training and resources to help teachers integrate these materials into their lessons. Regularly update the resources to ensure they remain useful. Create a platform for teachers to share their experiences and tips on using BANAS resources, which will encourage collaboration and improve teaching practices.

Schools may continue implementing hands-on workshops, mentorship programs, and integrate these resources into lesson plans.

Providing online training, creating a sharing platform for teachers, and making BANAS resource training a regular part of professional development are key.

Although the results indicate no significant relationship between teachers' level of awareness on BANAS non-print resource and pupil performance, schools may keep BANAS resources up-to-date and aligned with current educational standards. By implementing these practices, schools can better support teachers in their roles and significantly boost student learning outcomes.

Although the results indicate no significant relationship between teachers' extent of utilization on BANAS non-print resource utilization and pupil performance, schools may establish a supportive environment for these resources. Providing technical support and ensuring that teachers have easy access to the latest BANAS materials will facilitate their integration into lessons.

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